

Effect of Parent Education and Involvement on Parental Attitudes Toward Children's Participation in Physical Activity

Mr. Sanket Vijay Nalkar¹ & Dr. Nishigandha Rameshwar Patil²

Corresponding Author – Mr. Sanket Vijay Nalkar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18898039

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to design a questionnaire to examine parents' outlook towards physical activity. Outlook means parents attitude, perception, behavior, awareness, motivation and knowledge towards their child physical activity. After participation in the physical activity program and workshop researcher was expected to examine the effect on parental outlook and their children's regularity in physical activity.

The developed questionnaire was given to parents of control and experimental group for pre test and posttest. Parental education-based workshop and 8-week physical activity program for children is given to experimental group. Information about task sheets, worksheets, Demonstration of exercises, information about importance of physical activity, how parent's involvement in child physical activity is important, information on exercise intensity and nutritional diet is given to parents in workshop.

The results show significantly increase in parent's outlook $t = 5.377$ at ($p = 0.001$), parent's attitude $t = 3.770$ at ($p = 0.001$), awareness and knowledge towards physical activity $t = 2.445$ at ($p = 0.017$) and activity preferences $t = 3.876$ at ($p = 0.001$). Results shows that no significant improvement in school help for motivation $t = 1.799$ at ($p = 0.077$). Significant correlation was not found in parent's outlook and children physical activity score.

Scores from this scale indicate that we can measure parent's outlook towards child physical activity participation and the designed program can change the outlook of the parents towards physical activity.

Keywords: Physical Activity, Outlook towards Physical Activity, attitude towards physical activity, workshop based parental education program.

Introduction:

Parents have the central role in encouraging their children to do physical activities. Their attitudes, views and performances toward physical activities can have strong effects on their children attitudes, views and performances (Ramezani-Nezhad et al., 2009). Kahn and Ramsey (2002) concluded that parents can encourage and create positive attitudes in their children to do or continue doing physical activities through regulating time and number of physical activities sessions, improving their

practice knowledge, increasing their support and creating self-esteem and confidence in their children to do physical activities. In another study (Zamatkin et al., 2004) reported that parent's attitudes toward physical activities have effects on children attitudes about their active participation in different types of physical activities. Li et al, (2007) found that parent's life-style has effect on healthy behaviors of their children and thus on some levels of their physical activities. They also reported in the study that parent's attitudes are one of the most effective

factors in determining children attitudes toward physical activities (Li et al., 2007). Clement, (2009) in a study reported a positive relation between parent's attitudes and children attitudes and behaviors.

Research Objectives:

The purpose of this study was to improve parent outlook towards physical activity. This study aimed:

1. To design a Questionnaire to examine parents' outlook towards physical activity.
2. To develop a workshop based parental education program for enhancing parents' outlook towards physical activity.
3. To develop physical activity program for students to be conducted by parents.
4. To conduct pre test and post test of parents' outlook towards physical activity through questionnaire.
5. To examine the outlook of parents towards physical activity.
6. To study the impact of physical activity program on students' regularity in participation in physical activity.
7. To study the effect of the workshop based parental education program on the parents' outlook towards physical activity.

Hypothesis of the Research:

H_{1.1} – Parental education and involvement in the intervention program significantly increase the parent outlook towards Physical Activity.

H_{1.2} – Parental education and involvement in PA program leads to significant increase in regularity in doing PA of children.

Research Questions:

Does involving parents with children in PA make difference in parent outlook and students regularity in doing physical activity every day?

Research Method:

For this research the researcher used experimental method. Treatment was given by using physical activity program. Pre test and post test was taken by using questionnaire about parents outlook towards physical activity.

This study used Pre-experimental design, in that pre-test - post-test non- equivalent group design. This design is often used in classroom experiments when experimental and control groups are approximately similar.

X → O1 → O3

C → O2 → O4

O1 and O3 were the pre test and post test of the Experimental group respectively.

O2 and O4 were pre test and post test of the control group respectively.

X- Treatment

C- Control group

Variables of the Study:

Independent variables - students PA program, workshop for parents, gender.

Dependent variables – outlook, parent involvement.

Population:

Present study will provide valuable information about parents of kindergarten students. For the current study the population was kindergarten students from Pune city. Population for this study is approximately 20000.

Sample of the Study:

For the current study Non-probability method is used in which purposive sampling technique is used. Researcher has selected students from Vidya valley school consisting 90 students from both Jr. KG and Sr. KG. For experimental and control group simple random sampling technique was used.

Initial stage I have selected 100 students out of which due to mortality and absentee in the final stage the total population remain in the sampling for analysis is 90.

Procedure:

1. Consent of school and parents to go ahead with the study.
2. Tool development procedure.
3. To develop physical activity program and conduct workshop.
4. Pre test: Parents will fill attitude towards physical activity questionnaire for pre test.
5. Data Collection: Daily physical activity program for students will be given and which will be taken by parents.
6. Post test: Parents will again fill up Physical activity questionnaire for post test.
7. Data Analysis: Comparison between pre test and post test to check effects of intervention program on parent's outlook towards physical activity. Part of the evaluation of this project is to investigate parent's attitude, perception, knowledge and awareness to their child involvement in Physical activity and the changes in these attitudes, knowledge, awareness as a result in this intervention.

Instrument Development:

Table 1: Factor wise outlook scale

Sr. No.	Factor	Sub factor	No. of Questions
1	Attitude and perception	Parents attitude towards PA	18
		Parents attitude towards their child PA	
		Parents perception towards PA	
2	Awareness, Knowledge, Motivation	Parents Awareness, Knowledge, Motivation towards their child PA	10
3	Activity Preferences	-	6
4	School help for Motivation	-	5

Pilot Study: The purpose of the pilot study was to find out validity and reliability of the instrument. The instruments were checked by the primary investigator, and instrument that were incomplete or were clearly not completed were discarded. Further corrections were made and the scale was refined.

Validation Study:

Data analysis for validity evidence based on internal structure:

Data from the collected 51 items were entered into an excel worksheet. Incomplete and unusable items will be discarded. Negatively coded items were reverse-coded before uploading data into SPSS.

Content validity evidence:

Six physical education teacher educators (PETE) professors were asked to complete a content validity study. Percentages agreement with the proposed factor was calculated for each item.

Reliability:

Twenty five teachers were asked to complete a reliability study. Test retest method was used to calculate the reliability of the scale. Correlation between pre test and post test is 0.87.

Table 2: Independent Samples Test: Change in outlook score

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means			
	F	Sig.	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Equal variances assumed	24.034	0.001	-5.304	88	0.001	-5.54743
Equal variances not assumed			-5.377	66.444	0.001	-5.54743

Independent Samples Test: Change in performance of factor 1

Equal variances assumed	43.346	0.001	-3.698	88	0.001	-2.45158
Equal variances not assumed			-3.770	52.288	0.001	-2.45158

Independent Samples Test: Change in performance of factor 2

Equal variances assumed	10.831	0.001	-2.405	88	0.018	-0.86364
Equal variances not assumed			-2.445	59.263	0.017	-0.86364

Independent Samples Test: Change in performance of factor 3

Equal variances assumed	14.283	0.001	-3.818	88	0.001	-1.56028
Equal variances not assumed			-3.876	62.687	0.001	-1.56028

Independent Samples Test: Change in performance of factor 4

Equal variances assumed	9.402	0.003	-1.773	88	0.080	-0.71542
Equal variances not assumed			-1.799	64.482	0.077	-0.71542

Research Question:

Present study has one research Question.

“Does involving parents with children in PA make difference in parent outlook and students regularity in doing physical activity every day?”

- (67%) parents assisted their children in doing the entire task given to them.
- They were involved in outdoor as well as indoor activities.
- Parents were involved in activities like walking (65%), cycling (58%), running (39%) and in ball games (26%).
- (32%) parents did swimming and mountain climbing (26%) with their child.
- Activities like cricket (5%), Frisbee (1%), were shown least interest and showed less participation from the parent's side.

- This program could act as a guide for parents who haven't been involved with their kid's physical activity.
- (60.86%) parents said that their involvement in their child's physical activity has increased.
- (39.13%) parents said that Child physical activity has increased.
- (32.60%) parents felt that their physical activity has increased due to this initiative.

Discussion:

- Attitude is closely related in positive manner with parental outlook (Smith, Wilson, Limbu).
- During experiment, attitude of the parent towards physical activity was also tried to develop.
- Awareness can affect the parent's performance. (Decker L.).

- Treatment program consists of information and lectures regarding physical activity, Nutrition, continuous follow up and feedback may increase parent's awareness towards physical activity.
- Motivation and continuous feedback also affect on parental attitude towards PA (Limbu).
- Knowledge regarding PA, nutrition, benefit of PA etc. was given to parents by providing information and lectures.
- Knowledge towards physical activity given to parents also affects the performance. (Wilson, Gillett, Lisowski & Disinger).
- Students did regular physical activity monitored by parents but has not reached at specific goal.
- Parent's involvement has definitely increased their child's physical activity.
- Parent's behavior (Wilson) was changed because of their outlook, attitude, knowledge and awareness (Wing).
- To sustain regularity in PA, we have to keep motivating them.
- Continuous health education should be provided to parents at schools.

Parents thought about the program:

- 73% parents said that tasks and range of exercises is satisfactory.
- 87% of the parents said that this is very good initiative by the school to bring exercise and sports to our everyday life.
- This is a good way for parents to think about their physical activity. It could act as a guide for parents who haven't been involved with their kid's physical activity. These activities will help children to achieve overall development.
- This program will develop the habit and interest in physical activities right from

their childhood and it will become the foundation for their healthy life.

Parents view about how the school can motivate:

- School should organize after or before school activity classes.
- Organize small races, events on monthly basis in school for parents and children. Parents will help sports teachers for organizing these competitions.
- Show news of current sports affairs.
- Show movies related to sports, lectures on benefits of sports and PA,
- School should give directions to children to be physically active. School can also call sportsman to visit school as a role model for students.
- School should send activity report more often and also offer school ground and premises for play in weekends.
- School can target one sport a month and parents could support that practical sport by taking about it at home and even playing it over the weekend.

Conclusion:

1. Parent's outlook towards physical activity can be measured by using developed questionnaire.
2. It was also concluded that the developed program consisting of workshop monitored child's Physical activity program enhanced parents outlook towards physical activity.
3. From the results obtained by pre test and post test, it was concluded that parent's attitude towards physical activity and parent's attitude towards their child's physical activity improved significantly.
4. Positive impact of the program was found on the parent's awareness and knowledge

towards physical activity and their activity preferences increased due the conducted program.

5. Significant correlation was not found in parent's outlook towards child physical activity participation and children physical activity score.
6. Involving parent's and educating them has lead to increase in their Physical activity.
7. In between control and experimental group no significant difference found in the school's help for motivation factor, quality of time spend by parents with child in doing physical activity and parents degree of satisfaction towards child physical activity.

Recommendations:

Based on study:

- Questionnaire and program is effective.
- This program can be implemented in school.
- This program is effective to develop parents outlook, attitude, knowledge and awareness towards Physical activity.

Based on Observation:

- The program should have lectures related to diet, exercise and physical activities and provide more informative workshops.
- Informative videos should be sent to parents, so that they can understand how to do proper exercises.
- Physical activity test may be administered to the parents and students before and after the program
- Instead of weekly physical activity worksheets daily and detailed worksheet may be provided.
- Physical activity tasks may be arranged more group oriented and more enjoyable so the activity will be more enjoyable.

For Further Research:

- Conduct the same research on large sample for generalization purpose.
- Conduct another research to find out which factors influence on parent's involvement.
- Research can be conducted on Parental diet and the impacts on children health.
- The role of peers and family on the physical activity levels and eating patterns of children.
- Conduct another research on Family mealtime and its impact on activity level.
- Some parents define physical activity as mostly being on a sports team and activities that involve competition and their child does not enjoy sports or competition, this may have a significant impact on how aware and supportive parents are of other physical activities and how encouraging they are of these activities, a research in this line should be conducted.
- How physically active children while playing outside, participating in after-school programs and various sports.

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